

USING MULTI-ENCODER NMT IN ENGLISH-MALAY TRANSLATION

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Abstract

Neural Machine Translation (NMT) is one of the most popular approaches for language translation. In this paper, we proposed to use multi-encoder NMT for English to Malay translation by using different resources as an extra information for NMT. TensorFlow is the existing toolkits that used in this research paper. By using multi-encoder NMT, we try to increase the BLEU score for a specific domain and general domain.

1 INTRODUCTION

Machine Translation (MT) is a process of translating text from a source language to a target language using a software. Nowadays, Neural Machine Translation (NMT) is the most popular state-of-the-art MT architectures used by many researchers. Unlike Statistical Machine Translation (SMT), NMT using a neural network to learn the translation patterns without a language model.

One of the most popular NMT uses an encoder-decoder architecture [1]. NMT has shown to give a better translation quality than SMT in many recent works [2]. However, NMT approached based on an encoder-decoder architecture also has its weaknesses, for example, the model requires more training data to be built, and out of vocabulary words.

In this paper, we are focused on multi-source encoder-decoder. Although some of the existing research works have been done for other researchers, for example, Dabre et al. [3] used to concatenate the source sentences to form a single long multi-source input sentence in multiple languages. Sutskever et al. [4] used long-short-term memory (LSTM) networks to re-score the 1000-best translations and this simple approach improve the BLEU score from 33.3% to 36.5%.

Figure 1: The encoder-decoder framework for neural machine translation (NMT) [4].

Zoph and Knight [5] built a multi-source machine translation model and train to maximize the probability of a target string.

Figure 2: Multi-source encoder-decoder model for MT [5].

Zhang et al. [6] proposed to extend the original encoder-decoder framework to multiple encoders and decoders. But, there is still have other methods to improve the quality of the translation in a hybrid model. So, the below sections will discuss on our proposed approach by using multi-source encoder-decoder in English-Malay translation.

2 PROPOSED WORK

In general, we use multi encoders to decode a sentence in English to Malay. The idea is to make use of the current information such as word frequency and part-of-speech for the sentences to assist the NMT in the translation. Each encoder will embed the meaning of the sentence as a vector and send it to a decoder. The decoder then processes the vectors and emit the translation. Before decoding, we normalized all the digits and mapped all the out-of-vocabulary (OOV) words to <UNK> and also added a list of a proper noun into the parallel text. The overall process shows in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Overview of the proposed approach.

The detail of the process for encoders and decoder shows in Figure 4.

Additionally, more than one NMT models can be combined through ensemble modeling to produce a better translation. The main idea of this approach is that each NMT has different errors in translation modeling. By using several shared models, the translation error can be reduced thus further improving the quality of the translation produced.

3 RESULTS

In the experiment, NMT decoder was based on Tensorflow 1.2, an open source software from Google. We used an English-Malay parallel text corpus [7] that contains 478 thousand parallel sentences for training the MT models.

There are two sets of testing data to test the result from a different domain. The first set is a specific domain that collects from past year exam questions from the School of Computer Science in University Science of Malaysia that contains 4,000 sentences and around 300kB. The second set is a general domain that collects from Malaysia's daily news called Malaysiakini that contains 3,070 sentences and around 450kB.

For NMT, a development set is required for the process of decoding. So, 2,000 sentences around 300kB for both source and target language from Malaysia’s daily news used for development data. All the training data, testing data, and development data have both Malay and English version.

The purpose of these pre-processing steps is to overcome the limitation of the NMT approach. The NMT used one hidden layer, 512 states, no drop-off, and with a vocabulary of 60 thousand words. Table 1 shows the BLEU score result.

Table 1: BLEU score result for NMT decoder.

Decoder	Specific Domain	General Domain
NMT	21.17%	41.75%

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